

Political Will as a Panacea for Good ... (Idoko, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10086352>

Political Will as a Panacea for Good Governance and National Development: An Overview of the 2022 Electoral Act in Nigeria

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Abstract

Studies have indicated that myriad of policies and programs initiated by political elite in Nigeria were geared towards national development and good governance. The passing of the 2022 Electoral Act is pursuant to the desire to entrench good governance and democracy in Nigeria. This work “Political will” a Panacea for Good Governance and National Development; an Assessment of the 2022 Electoral Act in Nigeria is aimed at assessing to what extent the political elite are willing to entrench good governance and development in Nigeria. The study adopted the decision-making theory as tool for analysis and analytical cum descriptive method of data collection. Information were collected for the purpose of describing and interpreting the willingness or otherwise of the elite in achieving goals of the Act, through textual methodology. Finding reveals that lack of political will of the elites is a major clog in attempts at entrenching of good governance in Nigeria. It is recommended therefore that elites in Nigeria be strictly guided by their oath of office, that is not to allow personal interest, ethnic consideration, political association or affiliation and region influence/interfere with decision they make but national interests.

Keywords: Political Will, Good Governance, National Development, Electoral Act, National Interest.

Introduction

Several scholars have written on the impact of colonial heritage on the nation Nigeria. This heritage according to Matthew and Holly (2022) has left deep scar on the country’s history. The question of the civil war between groups within the nations border, political rift, regional mutual suspicion has characterized relation between a nation of about 250 ethnic nationalities bound together not by their consent but colonial contraption of the Berlin conference (Oluwaseun, 2021). Having understood this precarious position, successive government since independence has put in place reform agendas and policy instruments in attempts at achieving ethno-regional balance. A centralizing nation building drive started in 1966 to 1979 through constitutional reform which introduced in the management of interethnic relations (Mustapha 2005). The 1979 federal character principles aimed at ensuring representation and power sharing is one of such management policies. However, efforts at reforming inter-ethnic relation and creating inclusive institutions have limited success. This lack of success is hinged on “political will”. Political will could be explained as the extent of committed support among key decision makers for a particular policy solution to a particular problem (Iori, A. et-al 2010). It should be noted that this concept (political will) is a complex one having many sides to achieving same. On the other hand, there is the authority, capacity and legitimacy of the key decision makers or reformers which is also dependent on whether those who want an outcome have the power and means to achieve it. There is also the question of commitment to preference.

Analyzing the passage of the 2022 electoral act, scholars have argued and criticized the premise of the then president Muhammadu Buhari withholding of assent to the bill. The basis of the criticism of withholding assent is on the willingness to improve on the electoral system. According to the former governor of Rivers state Nyesom Wike, the refusal for the president to assent is based on the inclusion of a clause which is not going to be favourable to the authorities. The clause he argued is the electronic transmission of results embedded in the act. He further argued that there is an opportunity for clauses in a bill to be further amended, citing the petroleum bill which was signed in spite of unresolved issues and bill sent back for an amendment (Nathaniel 2021). Ayida (1987) had argued that Nigeria is a land of promise and hope in Africa and basically stable and structurally well balanced but that ominous signs of crack are ever present. He further argued given the right leadership, the cracks will be overcome.

According to Kevin Casaszamoia, the secretary general of the International institute for Democracy and Electoral Assistance (IDEA), a sub unit of the United Nations assembly, in a press release, opined that “in order to protect democracy, we must protect election” (UN office, 2023). It follows therefore that election and electoral processes must be seen to be

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credible to have integrity and acceptability. The electoral process, which includes reforms of electoral laws are ideal and integral part of the democratic process. A faulty electoral system results to maladministration or bad governance.

Theoretical Framework

The fulcrum of decision-making theory lies in the ability to choose between alternatives with emphasis on goal-directed guide with predetermined criteria or what could be referred to as means-ends rationality (Simon 1947). The theoretical framework adopted in this work is the decision-making approach. The theory seeks to explain how decision are made by states as it relates to their national interest. Herbert A. Simon, James G. March, Guetzkow H, Richard Synder, Bruk, H.W. and Sapin, B. are well known in this field (Johari, 1963). Richard Synder and his associates pioneered the decision-making approach to the study of foreign policy and policies generally (verma 2001). The basic assumption of the approach is that policies are not made by states but by individuals who act on behalf of the state. The analysis of state behavior centres on these individuals and groups who represent their states. The approach discusses decision makers as individuals who arrive at their decision by confronting their values with their image of the environment. It utilizes both internal and external factors as they influence decision (Ojo and Sesay 2022). This theory is relevant to this work because the analysis of state behaviour centres on individual and group who represent their state. All political actions are undertaken by concrete human being and we should view the world from the point of the perspectives of the persons responsible for taken decision. For instance, the National Assembly as an arm of government has identified personalities and not abstract contraptions. The behavior of these individuals at the National Assembly as well as their values and perceptions play significant role in the formulation of Nigeria policies. This theory suffers some limitations because it concentrates exclusively upon image and perception of decision makers and the psychological environment and ignores the objective realities that these reflect. It merely helps us to understand the mechanics but does not provide a satisfactory explanation of the broader aspect of policy. It does not show how the responses from the operational environment affect policy powers in its course. The theory does not adequately explain how decision are made in crisis situation when reactions to threatening problems are drastic and some are intuitive with no time to analyze issues critically.

Synder's contribution is said to be the most outstanding in explaining decision making. He refutes the static analysis as adopted by the system analyst and structural functionalists. He prescribes a process analysis capable of dealing with dynamic situation. A process analysis should explain the situation and reasons for the situation why it evolves in a particular way. He opines that in order to understand the dynamics of political actions, the world should be viewed from the perspective of persons responsible for taking decision. He is concerned mainly with who made the key decision that gave rise to a particular action and how to assess the intellectual and internal processes which decision makers followed to reach their decision. Decision making in relation to policy is an elite thing, therefore the decision making begins by considering all alternatives, causes of action and their consequences and then decide which of the alternatives will maximize her value. Through the decision-making theory, the goals of Nigeria as a state and her national interest are identified by the objective circumstance. The behavior of the Nigeria state is therefore the behavior of the decision makers as such the state action is the action of its officials. Notwithstanding the short coming of the decision-making theory it remains a useful tool of analysis as it pertains to policy.

Political Will, Good Governance and National Development

Political will presupposes a commitment to real or sincerely perceived solution to problems. In as much as the concept is often used in political discussions as rhetorical, it remains an ambiguous concept. Scholars have approached the definition of this concept using varying approaches and categories. Harmergen (1998) see it as a likelihood of reform; kpundeh (1998) perceives it as a demonstrated credible intent of political actors, whether elected or appointed leaders, civil society watchdogs, and stakeholder groups etc, to attack perceived causes or effort at a systematic level. Brinkerhoff and Kulibaba (1999) perceived political as a commitment of actors to undertake actions, to achieve a set objective and to sustain the cost of these actions overtime. Rose and Gveely (2006) perceive political will as a sustained commitment of politicians and administrators to invest political resources to achieve specific objectives. It is clear, the corollary of political will to good governance, but very often politicians fail to adopt and implement policies that they are aware, are necessary for sustained economic, social and political development. Most times, the political elite knows what is right but is willing to go against what they believe is right to fall lock-step with their party or their campaign finances. They are unwilling to follow their conscience but rather political expediency. It is the antithesis of political will which translates to lack of one. The political elites therefore must ensure that integrity policies aimed at preventing corruption and fostering high standards of behavior, helping to reinforce the credibility and legitimacy of those involved in policy decision making, safeguarding the public interest and restoring confidence in the policy making process. The constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 as amended 2011 (akande 2010), stipulates

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provisions aimed at enhancing preserving and protecting the people's right which ultimately translates to good governance. There is no gain saying a correlation exist between political will and good governance and development. Though there exist no one all-embracing definition of the term good governance; the United Nation refer governance to every activity of all political and administrative authority to govern their country. Thus, generally, governance has the meaning, the decision-making process and the process of determining which policy or policies will best suit a particular purpose or circumstance, (UCLG ASPAC, 2023).

From the above eight principles are deducible from the character of good governance, viz participation, rule of law, transparency, responsiveness, consensus, equity and inclusiveness, effectiveness and efficiency and accountability (UCLG ASPAC, 2023). Considering the 2023 Electoral Act, its correlation to good governance and development, YIAGA Africa in their report on the 2023 elections in Nigeria, titled 2023 election; dashed hope? Counsel the electoral body to rebuild public confidence. According to them, the big lesson from the 2023 general election in Nigeria is that electoral reform can deliver credible election if stakeholders, especially Independent National Electoral Commission and political parties comply with rules and guidelines (Ewepu, 2023).

Politics of the 2022 Electoral Act in Nigeria

The electoral act of 2022 has come with so much controversy. The reason is in view of the president (then) Muhammadu Buhari's refusal to assent to the bill at a time in which the electorates and Nigeria believed it would have been so signed, so as to give credibility to the electoral process. No law has created such anxiety and agitation as the electoral act, as it was supposed to guide the conduct of the 2019 general elections. According to the president, his refusal to sign was premised on the fact that the electoral process had begun and signing the act to guide the 2019 electoral process would open a flood gate of litigation as it would be seen as ultra-vires (business hallmark 2019). He further argues that the national assembly must include a clause indicating that if he signs the act, it would not be used to regulate the upcoming 2019 election. More so, the ECOWAS protocol which Nigeria is a signatory forbids members from replacing or changing the rules of an election, less than six months to election except majority of the parties agree to same. Assuming but not conceding that he was right recourse to the ECOWAS protocol was superfluous for he did not explore the window of having to consult with other political parties before declining assent. Conceding that it was his right to veto any bill passed by the national assembly, this has to be done judiciously in the interest of the public; the controversies that the decline of assent generated exacerbated the aggravated political cleavages in the country and putting the legitimacy of the process in jeopardy, his action capable of sending wrong signal to the international community of his commitment to free, fair and credible elections. It has been argued that the former president Muhammadu Buhari's decline to assenting to the electoral act in 2018 was a clear demonstration of lack of political will. As noted earlier, the political elites know what is right but are unwilling to follow their conscience but rather political expediency. This was exactly what was demonstrated during the build up to the signing of the electoral act.

Conclusion

There is no gain saying the advantages of the improvement in the regulations guiding electoral process envisaged in the signing of the electoral act of 2022 in Nigeria; on one hand, it enhances the realization of the goals of the united nations in election, that is sustainable development, peace and security, human rights and gender equality (UN office 2021). In the face of the much talked about controversy surrounding the withdrawal of assent to signing the 2022 electoral act in 2018, settled, there is a new controversy which is generating another debate and is capable of creating and or causing legal crisis; that is the conflicting sections in the 2022 electoral act and the independent national electoral commission guidelines for the conduct of election, particularly sec 62(1) & (2) and clause 38 respectively. These sections seem to conflict each other in the mode of transmission of election result. Whereas one gives strength to electronically transmitted result, the other seems to water it down. This controversy if not taken care of, is capable of derailing the gains of the goal of the reform.

Recommendations

It is expedient therefore that in achieving good governance and national development, policy makers must:

1. Adhere strictly to their oath of office as contained in chapter 333 of the Nigerian oath act 2003.
2. Legal professionals and experts should be engaged to draft legal instrument to avoid conflict of laws.
3. Every successive government must as a matter of policy draw out electoral reform agenda it intend to carry out within a time frame with the view to improving upon flaws observed during the run up to and after its election year.

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Reference

- Akande, JODL. (2010) "The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (1999) as Amended (2011)." Lagos: M.J. Business Hallmark. Available at: <https://hallmarknews.com/electoral-act-a-nation-still-in-search-of-credible-election-editorial>
- Ayida, A.A (1987) "Reflection on Nigeria Development." Lagos: Malthouse Press Limited, Heinmann Educational Books.
- Brinkerhoff, D.W and Kulibaba, N.P (1999) "Identifying and Assessing Political Will for Anticorruption Efforts." USAID's Implementing Policy Change Project Working Paper No.13 (January). Accessed on 29/6/2023. Available at: <https://www.USaid.gov/our-work-democracy-and-governance/publication/IPC/wp-13-ms.pdf>
- Ewepu, G. (2023). 2023 Elections: INEC, Other Actors Failed to Meet Nigerians' Expectation. <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2023/07/2023-elections> incotheractors-failed-to-meet-nigerians-epectations-yiaga-africa
- Hammergen, L. (1998) "Political Will, Constituency Building and Public Support in Rule of Law Programs." Field Support and Research; US Agency for International Development (August). Accessed on 29/6/2023. Available at: <https://pdf.USaid.gov/pdfdocs/PNACD023.pdf>
- Kpundeh, S.J (1998) "Political Will in Fighting Corruption." In Corruption and Integrity Improvement Initiatives in Developing Countries. New York: UNDP, 91-110.
- Lori, A. et al. (2010) "Buhari Has No Excuse for Not Signing the Electoral Act Amendment Bill, Says Wike." Available at: <https://www.channelstv.com/2021/12/20/buhari-has-no-excuse-for-not-signing-electoral-act-ammendment-bill-says-wike>
- Matthew, S and Holly, D (2020) "Nigeria Tribes and Ethnic Groups." Available at: <https://study.com/academy/lesson/nigeria-ethnic-groups.html-nigeria-tribes-and-ethnic-groups>
- Mustapha, A.R (2005) "Ethnic Structures, Inequality, and Governance of Public Sector in Nigeria." Centre for Research on Equality, Human Security, and Ethnicity (CRISE, Oxford). Available at: <https://gsdrc.org/document-library/ethnic>
- Oluwaseun, S. (2021) "Complete List of the Over 250 Ethnic Groups in Nigeria by States." Available at: <http://www.experts.ng/blog/ethnic-groups-in-nigeria>
- Rose, P and Greeley, M (2006) "Education in Fragile States: Capturing Lessons and Identifying Good Practices." Development Cooperation Directorate; Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development. Accessed on 29/6/2023. Available at: <https://www.ids.ac.uk/download.cfm>
- United Cities and Local Government and Asia Pacific Good Governance: Definition and Characteristics <https://uclg-aspac.org/goodgovernance-definition-and-characteristics> retrieved 20/7/2023.
- United Nations Office (2021) "Could This Be a Conflict: Section 62(1) and (2), Electoral Act, 2022, and Clause 387 of the Regulations and Guidelines for the Conduct of Elections, 2022." Available at: <https://lawpavillion.com/blog/could-this-be-a-conflict-section-62-1-2-electoral-act-2022-and-clause-38-of-the-regulation-and-guidelines-for-the-conduct-of-election-2022>.